

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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PROCESS IMPROVEMENT FOR SCREENING PATIENTS IN URGENT CARE

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Demands for immediate access to health care has increased the volume of patients that the Urgent Care setting is receiving. Emergency Departments (EDs) and Urgent Care Centers (UCC) provide health care services to patients who walk-in without scheduled appointments. Because some patients present to the UCC experiencing critical or other life-threatening symptoms, it is essential to have an efficient patient screening process in place to be able to identify critical conditions and respond promptly. The purpose of this project was to provide triage nurses with education to enhance triage skills, provide an efficient method of gathering key assessment data during the triage process, and establish a standardized workflow process for triage in the UCC to maximize efficiency and increase patient safety. The new UCC triage process was implemented as a pilot with all clinic registered nurses (RNs) and included an online triage training module and an in-person review of triage assessment training. Additionally, there was a component of the protocol (red flag symptom list) that was reviewed with service representatives as this impacted their check-in workflow.

Pre-implementation data revealed that patients who checked in to be seen in Urgent Care and required a triage assessment, were not flagged appropriately. Eleven percent of the patient charts were appropriately identified and documented as “red flag”, which indicated a need for immediate treatment. Eighty-nine percent of the qualifying patients were not triaged. Additionally, triage nurses showed a compliance rate of 43% for appropriate triage documentation. There was a 0% compliance rate for documenting all vital signs.

Post implementation data showed improvement in all areas. Appropriate flagging of charts occurred at a 42% compliance rate compared to only 11% at baseline.

Compliance rate for appropriate use of the documentation template went from 43% to 98% post implementation. Completion of the full set of vital sign documentation compliance rate increased from 0% to 75%.

An efficient triage protocol is essential for busy urgent care centers. This project resulted in a change, which increased patient safety in addressing urgent symptoms. It is now time to more widely disseminate this intervention.

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BACKGROUND

Emergency Departments (EDs) and Urgent Care Centers (UCC) provide health care services to patients who walk-in without scheduled appointments, seeking care for episodic conditions or exacerbations of chronic conditions (McNeeley, 2012; Weinick, Burns, & Mehrotra, 2010). As in the case of EDs, the acuity of patients who walk into UCCs varies. It is not unusual for patients to present to UCC experiencing critical or other life-threatening symptoms (Siegfried, Jacobs, & Olympia, 2019). Therefore, it is essential to have an efficient patient screening process in place to be able to identify critical conditions and respond promptly (i.e. initiate treatment, stabilize the patient, discharge or transfer to ED). This screening process is known as triage and it marks the beginning of the UCC throughput (patient flow through the department) and treatment experience for a patient. Triage involves a designated registered nurse (RN) who performs a focused assessment of a patient's condition to determine the priority of need for treatment or medical intervention (Falconer et al., 2018). When a patient is not triaged timely and accurately, or the essential triage information is not gathered and documented, the medical intervention and disposition of the patient can be delayed. A delay in care can lead to a variety of poor outcomes. There may be delays in being able to move patients to the appropriate treatment area, and delays in obtaining doctor orders, which can lead to the worsening of symptoms, increased morbidity, and potentially death (Johnson, Motavalli, Gray, & Kuehn, 2014).

Despite the similarities between EDs and UCCs, they are two separate entities equipped with different resources (i.e. equipment, medications, etc.) to treat patients. Urgent Care Centers can be privately owned or can be part of a hospital system.

Privately owned facilities operate as free-standing healthcare centers and are bound by certain state regulations and/or accreditation bodies. Hospital-owned facilities can be regulated by the same federal and state regulations as EDs and they can also be non-regulated (Bitterman, 2006; Department of Managed Healthcare, 2019; Siegfried et al., 2019). Regardless of the applicable regulations, UCCs provide a service that is increasingly sought after as patients opt to use UCCs rather than seek appointments with their primary care physician (PCP) or go to the ED (Llovera et al., 2019). Between 2008 and 2015, there was an increase of 119% in patient visits to UCCs (Siegfried et al., 2019). Of this reported growth, only about 3% of the patients were transferred to higher levels of care. Evidence indicates that a significant percentage of patients are assessed and treated at the UCC level which reduces the volume of patients seen in the ED for minor acuity conditions (Siegfried et al., 2019; Weinick et al., 2010, Yee, Lechner, & Boukus, 2013). As the UCCs continue to see an increase in patient visits per year and the symptom acuity of walk-in patients continue to vary, it is essential to ensure that there is a standard process for prioritizing care (Alkon, 2018).

Although there is no standardized triage process for use in UCCs (i.e. triage documentation, acuity tool, assessment practices, etc.), research indicates that UCCs function similarly to EDs (UCAOA, 2018; Sanders, 2000). Therefore, effective standard triage mechanisms already in place in EDs could be beneficial in UCC settings. A standardized triage process minimizes the risk of miscommunication of patient information and erroneous assessments (Malmstrom et al., 2017; Resnik, 2019). Previous research has identified that a triage process with clear, concise, and consistent communication between healthcare providers helps minimize the risk for delay of care

and poor patient outcomes (Hitchcock et al., 2014). When patients are not triaged promptly and wait an extended amount of time to be assessed, there is a high risk for delay of treatment, patient(s) leaving without being seen, and an increased risk for negative patient outcomes (Johnson et al., 2014; Martino et al., 2011).

Problem Statement

A busy UCC located within a shared medical office building in Southern California is the entryway to healthcare for most patients. The UCC does not require a prior appointment and services patients on a walk-in basis. This UCC is not located on the same grounds as a hospital or an Emergency Department. Patients requiring higher level of care, once identified, would need to be transported via ambulance to the nearest hospital. The UCC serves an average of 250 patients a day and 350 patients during flu season (Private Urgent Care Patient Volume Report, 2018). The physical layout of the urgent care consists of a waiting room, a reception desk (facing the lobby), a separate desk area adjacent to the reception desk for the triage nurse, 11 exam rooms, and 4 observation bay areas. While in the observation rooms, patients are closely monitored while they receive IV fluids, medications, or wait to be transferred to the ED.

The UCC offers patients radiology, laboratory, medical and surgical services (i.e. open wound injuries, incision & drainage, laceration repairs, toenail removals, etc.) and provides nurse visit care (wound care, suture removals, injections, TB readings). Staffing is volume-based and consists of an administrative team (2 executives, 2 medical physician leaders, 1 manager, 20 medical doctors (internal medicine/family practice/ED), 10 physician assistants, 13 registered nurses, 6 licensed vocational nurses, and various on-call service representatives.

The intake process at the UCC begins when the patient checks-in with a service representative upon entering the department. The service representatives collect patient registration information, including the patient's chief complaint (or symptom). If a patient checks in with a symptom that is located on the "red-flag" list (i.e. chest pain, shortness of breath.), the patient is immediately sent to see the triage nurse, who sits adjacent to the service representatives in the waiting room area. Patients who do not check in with red-flag symptoms are booked to see a provider and wait in the lobby to be called in. The triage nurse has a visual of all the patients walking in and those who are sitting in the waiting room. The triage nurse scans through the chief complaint list of patients waiting and prioritizes them for a triage assessment. There is currently no standardized process for the screening assessment performed by the triage nurse. Each triage nurse performs assessments based on individual nursing experience. As a result, assessment and documentation lacks consistency. The information collected by the triage nurse is reviewed by a provider (i.e. doctors, physician assistants) who then initiates treatment. Because assessment and documentation are inconsistent, missing essential data may lead to delay of care with complications and poor patient outcomes (Christensen et al, 2016; Falconer, Karuppan, Kiehne & Rama, 2018; Johnson et al., 2014).

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this quality improvement project was to adapt and adopt a triage training protocol (currently used for phone triage in primary care departments) for use in the UCC and standardize the process for triage. This was implemented as a pilot which included an online triage training module required of all registered nurses in the UCC. The triage training included a six-minute video demonstration of how to conduct a

focused assessment. It provided the triage nurses with an efficient method of gathering key assessment data during the triage process. In addition to the online training module, documentation templates were reviewed and introduced to the department to guide the triage assessment and standardize the data that was collected and recorded. Consolidation of the multiple existing red flag lists (i.e. list of symptoms that are considered emergent and requiring triage assessment) standardized information used in the front-end check-in process. The combination of these interventions made up the workflow process for triage in the UCC to maximize triage efficiency and decrease the risk for delay of care and complications.

SUPPORTING FRAMEWORK

Evidence supports the importance of triage education, training, and process standardization (Hitchcock et al., 2014). Obtaining the correct assessment information to determine patient urgency is a critical step in ensuring patient safety (Malmstrom et al., 2017). The use of a framework is helpful in ensuring a smooth transition and sustainability of the new process. This quality improvement project was guided by the Plan Do Study Act (PDSA) Model. The PDSA Model consists of four recurring stages that guide the processes involved in quality improvement projects. The first stage (*Plan*) begins with the planning of the intervention once a problem has been identified. The second stage (*Do*) is implementing the intervention. The third stage is (*Study*), which involves evaluating the outcomes of the intervention. The final stage is (*Act*), which is to actively work to improve or sustain the intervention (Taylor et al., 2014). The PDSA model has been utilized in several healthcare settings and is considered a reliable and

valid method for implementation of an intervention (Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2018; Langley et al, 2009; Taylor et al., 2014).

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework: Plan, Do, Study, Act, (PDSA) Model (Langley et al., 2009). *Permission to use model was granted by the Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI). Application of PDSA to Project (see Appendix A).*

Model for Improvement

The project purpose is the first step of the model for improvement. The project interventions were the workflow process for triage in the UCC to maximize triage efficiency (improve patient check in to triage time) and decrease the risk for delay of care and complications. To measure if this change was an improvement compared to the current process, baseline and post-implementation data were collected and analyzed. The data included a knowledge check assessing triage training retention, chart audits verifying

that triage documentation templates were used, and spot checks observing the triage assessment skills of the nurses.

Plan

In the planning stage of the project, a review of the state regulations that apply to UCC were performed. There was also an internal review conducted to assess the current UCC screening practices. Identified gaps from this review (i.e. inconsistent documentation, the risk for delay of care, triage training deficits, extended wait times for patients to be triaged, extended wait times during triage) and suggestions for modifications were discussed with the key stakeholders of this project. The stakeholders included department leadership, the education department, the compliance department, and physician leaders. After the findings and suggestions for modifications to the current triage process were discussed, approval for final training protocols and documentation of assessments were obtained from department physician leaders each step of the way.

Do

Once the problems or gaps in triage were identified and approval from stakeholders had been obtained, a secondary meeting was scheduled with the department managers and supervisors to discuss the following steps. This included a review of the multiple red flag lists currently used in the department to consolidate it to a single list of “red flag” symptoms. The single list was compiled and presented to the physician leaders of the department for approval. This step was an important part of the initial screening process and eliminated potential confusion resulting from having to reference multiple lists. During this part of the process, it was essential to note that communication about this initiative is key in keeping the department engaged and obtaining buy-in (from

stakeholders and staff). Following the consolidation of the red flag lists, a collaborative meeting was scheduled between UCC management team and the department educator. The discussion included a roll-out plan for the triage training protocols including assessment training and documentation.

Study

To evaluate the effectiveness of the triage protocols, chart audits were performed pre and post implementation. To evaluate the effectiveness of the triage assessment training, the appropriate use of the red flag list, and whether there was a change in identification of patients requiring timelier triage, chart audits and “spot-checks” (unannounced documented observations) were performed by the supervisor on site. The data obtained from these chart audits and spot-checks were analyzed to identify any possible gaps and need for further training.

Act

Upon review and implementation of the modified triage protocols and assessment training, it is necessary to evaluate whether the intended aim was met or not met. This will be determined by the analyzed data obtained from the chart audits and spot checked performed post-implementation. During this last phase of the PDSA model, it will also be important to determine how staff will maintain triage assessment and documentation competency moving forward. If the project aim was not met, a secondary PDSA cycle would need to be implemented. To determine the next plan of action, it would be necessary to review the barriers or gaps identified during the first PDSA cycle.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

A literature review was conducted utilizing the databases: CINAHL, PubMed, Google Scholar, CSUF Library Article One Search, Agency for Health Care Research and Quality (AHRQ) and Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI) websites. Database search terms included urgent care, urgent care center or clinics, emergency department or emergency room, triage, triage protocols, urgent care triage tools, delay of care, timely triage, inadequate acuity, mistriage and under-triage, and emergency room triage. Mistriage occurs when critical symptoms are not identified by the nurse during the triage assessment. Under-triage occurs when patient symptoms are accurately prioritized. Articles were reviewed by title, abstract, and relevance to the subject for this project. Search limits included: journals published from 2014 to 2019, peer-reviewed, and written in English.

A secondary literature search was conducted to evaluate the use and efficacy of the urgent care triage protocol(s) and its impact on urgent care operations and efficiency. This search was conducted utilizing the databases: CINAHL, PubMed, EBSCO, Google Scholar, and CSUF Library Article One Search. Database search terms included: triage tool to determine disposition, urgent care evaluation tools, quality improvement evaluation of triage tool, spot-checks or observations, and chart audits. There were no search limits used (See Table 1).

Table 1

Initial Search Strategy

Topic	Search Terms	# Found
Urgent Care	☒ Urgent Care Center or Urgent Care Clinics	
	☒ Emergency Department OR Emergency Room	15, 347
	☒ Urgent Care and Triage Tools	
Triage	☒ Triage Tool	18
	☒ Acuity Screening Tools	
	☒ Emergency Department Triage Regulations	
	☒ Urgent Care Triage Algorithms	
	☒ Triage Documentation	
	☒ Triage Protocols	
	☒ Urgent Care and Triage Tools	
Evaluation	☒ Urgent care evaluation tools	2
	☒ Quality improvement evaluation of triage tool	
	☒ Spot-checks or observations/ Triage Observation	
	☒ Chart audits	
Google	☒ Urgent Care Center or Urgent Care Clinics	247,00
Scholar		0

	☒ Emergency Department OR Emergency Room	
CSUF One	☒ Triage Tool	
Search	☒ Acuity Screening Tools	507
	☒ Emergency Department Triage Regulations	
	☒ Urgent Care Triage Algorithms	
Agency for Health Care Research and Quality (AHRQ)	☒ Urgent Care Triage	99
Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI)	☒ Urgent Care Triage	16

Urgent Care Utilization

Urgent care centers (UCC) are often used for a variety of reasons. Patients may need to see a Primary Care Provider (PCP) for a same day appointment; however, these appointments may not be available. The PCP hours of operation are also limited, typically open during the day on weekdays. Thus, seeking care at a UCC allows patients

an alternative option for convenient access to medical care without an appointment.

UCCs also typically have extended hours and are often open on the weekends. These factors attract increasing numbers of patients to seek medical care from a UCC instead of the patient's PCP (Llovera et al., 2019; Siegfried et al., 2018).

As the patient demand for medical care increases and PCP access is limited, the patient volume shifts to emergency departments (EDs) and UCCs (Siegfried et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2015). This shift creates overcrowding which is a systemwide ED issue.

Overcrowding occurs when the demand (i.e. a high volume of patients) exceeds the capacity and available resources (i.e. staffing, available beds, etc.) to safely and efficiently care for patients (Aacharya, Gastmans, & Denier, 2011; Rowe et al., 2011).

This ED systemwide issue leads to long patient wait times, increased risk for symptom worsening, increased risk of poor patient outcomes or death, and decreased patient satisfaction (Hitchcock et al., 2014; Van Der Linden, Meester, & Van Der Linden, 2016; Wolf et al., 2017). The shift of patients from PCPs to EDs, has similarly impacted UCC's, leading to the need for additional facilities (Beaton, 2018; Lee, Lechner, & Boukus, 2013; Llovera et al., 2019).

Patients who seek care in UCCs are able to receive same day care at a lower cost, often with shorter wait times than in the EDs (Llovera et al., 2019). According to the American Academy of Urgent Care Medicine, there are over 9,000 UCCs (walk-in, standalone) with approximately 50 to 100 UCC's opening each year (Siegfried et al., 2018). Studies have shown that a UCCs location and proximity to an ED will decrease the number of patients presenting at the ED with low acuity symptoms (i.e. pharyngitis, bronchitis, etc.) (Llovera et al., 2019; Van Donk, Tanti, & Porter, 2016). The convenience and

accessibility of obtaining same day or immediate access to medical care continues to attract a growing number of patients in the UCCs. Despite the lack of published recommendations for triage processes specific to UCCs, there are many recommendations for EDs regarding standardized triage process (Christensen et al., 2016; Falconer et al., 2018; Siegfried et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2015). This has allowed for ED strategies to be analyzed and adapted by department leaders for UCC settings. (Christensen et al., 2016; Falconer et al., 2018; Unwin et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2015).

Triage

The initial patient screening process, which marks the beginning of throughput into the ED and UCC, is referred to as Triage. It typically consists of a designated area staffed by a registered nurse (RN). The duties of the RN include assessment of the patient's signs and symptoms and prioritization of their acuity (severity of symptoms) in order to be evaluated by a medical provider. It is the recommendation of the Emergency Nurses Association (ENA) that RNs who are deployed to triage possess specific qualifications. Triage RNs should have a minimum of one year of ED experience, receive assessment training and maintain skills competency, and receive mentorship with an experienced preceptor in order to enhance their triage knowledge and skills (Emergency Nurses Association, 2019).

Triage Documentation

One essential component of triage is the standardization of the documentation method used for capturing assessment data collected by the RN. Triage documentation in the electronic health record (EHR) is a form of communication between the triage RN and the treatment team (i.e. other RNs, LVNs, physicians, etc.) that facilitates a seamless

transition of care for patients (Falconer et al., 2018). One study found that use of the EHR system to document initial triage data improved provider access to the patient's information and improved timely treatment (Martino et al., 2011). Accuracy of triage documentation is crucial for decreasing delays in care (Falconer et al., 2018; Martino et al., 2011). It was also found to decrease patient wait time, increase patient satisfaction, and decrease patients leaving the ED without being seen (Christensen et al., 2016; Falconer et al., 2018; Unwin et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2015).

Innovative Triage Processes

Evidence shows that there are a variety of innovative triage processes (or strategies) available for EDs, which includes nurse-led triage utilizing the emergency severity index (ESI) tool, pivot nurse triage model, and triage and treat approach (also referred to as rapid medical exam) to name a few (Gilboy, Tanabe, Travers, & Rosenau, 2012; Gardner et al., 2017; Llovera et al., 2018; McHugh, Krinsky, & Sharma, 2018; Miles & Naumann, 2004; Van Donk et al., 2016). The nurse-led triage process involves an RN performing an assessment utilizing the ESI tool, which is used to rate patient acuity. The tool helps the triage nurses to prioritize the order in which a patient will be evaluated by the provider (Gilboy et al., 2012; Emergency Nurses Association, 2019).

The pivot nurse model was initiated as a pilot project at an urban, level II trauma and stroke center in, New Jersey. The model involved a designated "greeter RN" that was assigned to assist patients as they walked into the ED. This nurse was responsible to collect limited assessment information (i.e. chief complaint, oxygen saturation, and heart rate) and direct the patient to the correct ED location for further care (Christensen et al., 2016). Some of the challenges or learnings from the initial pilot launch were identified as

follows; the pivot nurse lacked a computer and desk to be able to document the focused triage assessment for patients, there was no transportation aide assigned to assist for those patients that required help moving from one area of the ED to the next, no communication method to facilitate transition of care with the rest of the team, and privacy was identified as a challenge due to the physical layout of the department (Christensen et al., 2016).

The triage and treat approach were also identified in the literature as an efficient innovative triage strategy. Deploying a physician or advanced practice provider in the triage area has been recommended, since it improves efficiency and reduces wait times for patients to receive a medical screening (Gardner et al., 2017; Iversen et al., 2016; Oredsson, 2012; Rowe et al., 2011). The role of a provider in triage is to listen to the RN perform her triage assessment and gather information required to initiate treatment orders as the patient is assessed. Once the triage RN concludes her initial assessment, the patient can then complete the provider's orders (i.e. point of care testing such as urine collection, blood work, x-rays, etc). This triaging strategy has improved throughput and decreased the total time patients spend in the ED (Gardner et al., 2017; Rowe et al., 2011). Another innovative strategy under the treat and treat category was identified as "fast track". This term was used to describe the process for expediting care for patients that have been identified as low acuity (i.e. medication refills, coughs, sore throat, etc.) by the triage RN. These lower acuity patients are assigned to see an advanced practice provider. These group of patients require one or no resources (x-Rays, IV fluids, etc.) facilitating a rapid triage and treat approach (Gardner et al., 2017; Iversen et al., 2016; Oredsson, 2012; Murrell, Offerman, & Kauffman, 2011).

Triage Education and Training

Implementation of a standardized triage process requires team buy-in, adequate training, a plan for ongoing validation of skill competency, and monitoring adherence to triage protocols (Aacharya et al., 2011; Gardner et al., 2017). The need for accurate and reliable triage has become more critical due to the growing volume of patients with more complex diseases (Brosinski, Riddell, & Valdez, 2017; Gilboy, Travers & Wuerz, 1999; Hinson et al., 2018;). Additionally, studies have identified that triage is a dynamic process that is constantly evolving, and therefore protocols and associated training should be reviewed regularly to ensure skills competency (Aacharya et al., 2011; Falconer et al., 2018; Martino et al., 2011). To ensure ongoing sustainability and competency, training is recommended every six months to one year (Aacharya et al., 2011; Falconer et al., 2018; Martino et al., 2011). Triage training was identified, in more than four studies, as being delivered to the staff by a clinical educator. This clinical educator collaborated with the department administrators (or leaders) to ensure there was a designated place and time allotment for monthly education to be completed (Aacharya et al., 2011; Falconer et al., 2018; Martino et al., 2011). The method for delivery of the staff education: included training of staff nurses via lectures (theory), case studies, small group discussions, simulations, and updates at staff meetings to reinforce learning (Aacharya et al., 2011; Delnavaz et al., 2018; Van Donk, 2016).

Evaluation Strategies

Limited studies were found on the evaluation measures for clinical skills specific to triage education and training. However, it was noted that several publications in their implications for further research, recommended addressing the need for additional education and ongoing evaluation of proper documentation (Falconer et al., 2018; Holmes et al., 2015; Tabor & Vaughn, 2017). The following were listed as evaluation tools: pre and post knowledge checks (to evaluate accuracy of triage acuity), direct observations of nurses performing triage assessments (to evaluate skills competency), chart reviews (to evaluate adherence to documentation protocols), and simulated triage scenarios (to evaluate the overall triage process) (Gilboy et al., 1999; Wolf & Faye, 2010). Individually or when used in a combination, as evaluation tools, they were found to be effective in measuring the need for additional skill training and as an effective strategy to maintain skills over time (Tabor & Vaughn, 2017; Wolf & Faye, 2010).

METHODS

The purpose of this quality improvement project was to adapt and adopt a triage protocol to maximize efficiency in a busy UCC. The project was implemented at a high patient volume UCC in Orange County which provides service to 300+ patients a day. The new UCC triage process was piloted with all clinic registered nurses (RNs) and registration clerks. The triage protocol included an online triage training module (10-minute video recording) and an in-person review of triage assessment training. The goals of this project were to provide the triage nurses with education to enhance triage skills, provide an efficient method of gathering key assessment data during the triage process, and establish a standardized workflow process for triage in the UCC to maximize efficiency.

Setting

The UCC was the pilot facility for this project. The focus was triage, which is carried out in the front reception lobby adjacent to the service representative's desk. Patients register for care as they walk into UCC and upon check-in, the service representative sends patients to the triage nurse and/or lobby depending on their urgency. There is a total of thirteen staff RNs who work at this UCC. Each of these RN's have an opportunity to rotate through triage, as this is part of a daily assignment. There is one triage RN assigned to each 8-hour shift (2 shifts per day).

Participants

The triage project participants included all UCC registered nurses. The RNs who work at the UCC have varying work backgrounds and skill experiences related to triage. Some nurses have only worked in ambulatory settings (outpatient clinics, non-hospital) their entire career, while others have worked on medical surgical floors, labor and delivery, emergency departments, or intensive care units (ICU). While there are nurses who have had experience with formalized triage processes, there are nurses who have never triaged patients prior to working in the UCC. Triage nurses with no prior experience had a greater need for triage training. It was essential to provide training and to standardize the triage process among all RNs, regardless of their prior experience. This would help strengthen the efficiency and quality in the triage process at the UCC and ensure that all RNs are engaged in the same practices. Charge nurses were included in the training so that they were aware of the content and performance expectations and that they would be able to train others. The Charge Nurses received additional training

focused on how to perform audits (chart audits and spot checks) to monitor compliance with the new triage process.

Ethical Considerations

Full disclosure of the quality improvement project was shared with all participant registered nurses and affiliated staff members in a staff meeting and through email communication and posted flyers in the department. Triage training was arranged at times that were convenient for participants.

Data collection and evaluation were completed, and the appropriate aggregate information was shared with nurse managers/supervisors, RNs, receptionists, and stakeholders (physician leaders and UCC management team). The data collected with potential personal/patient health information (PHI) was kept confidential. An Institutional Review Board (IRB) application was submitted to the California State University at Fullerton IRB as well as to the organization's IRB committee before the start of the project. Both IRB's approved this project.

Usual Triage Process

Patients enter the UCC and report to the receptionist at the front desk. The receptionists collect chief complaint information from patients, refer to their "red flag" lists (the department service receptionists have three red flag lists of symptoms requiring immediate triage) and follow their protocol to direct the patient to the lobby or to triage. The triage nurse then performs a focused assessment on the patient who is identified as having "red flag" symptoms, collects information about the patient's chief complaint (presenting symptom) and determines the acuity level based on their perception of the patient's presentation. The nurse then proceeds to document the patient information

gathered. Depending on the triage nurse who is assigned that day and their perception of patient acuity level, the patient is either taken immediately to an exam room to be seen by a provider or, if the acuity does not seem to be emergent (requiring immediate treatment or medical care) the patient will be directed to sit in the lobby until a room is available. All patients who are directed to sit back in the lobby are instructed to notify the triage nurse or receptionist if their condition changes or worsens. The amount of time each patient waits to be assessed by the triage nurse varies based upon the nurse's experience with triage and the amount of time it takes the nurse to collect and document the patient's information, the number of patients that are waiting to be triaged, and the acuity level of the patients waiting to be seen. It currently takes the triage nurse between five to ten minutes to perform an assessment on a patient requiring triage. Triage nurses with limited triage expertise take longer to complete this process, particularly for pediatric triage assessments (Emergency Nurses Association, 2017). A delay in triage for one patient impacts other patients who are waiting to be assessed. The risk is that patients who check in with an emergent symptom (i.e. chest pain, shortness of breath, stroke symptoms, etc.) may have to wait up to ten minutes or longer to be called by the triage nurse. Although patients who check in with emergent symptoms (symptoms listed in the red flag list, see Appendix C) will be prioritized for an assessment before a patient that checks in with a non-urgent symptom (i.e. abdominal pain, sore throat, cough, etc.), more than ten minutes for a patient that may be having a heart attack or stroke is too long (American Heart Association, 2019)

New Triage Process

The project to adapt and adopt a new triage process and maximize efficiency in the assessment process for patients in triage included several components. The adapt phase consisted of consolidating the three red flag symptom list into a single, one sheet document. This minimizes the risk for confusion and decreases the risk for missing a red flagged symptom. Having multiple reference lists is confusing when service receptionists are checking in over 200 patients a day. The adapt phase for the triage nurses included establishing a standardized workflow process for triage in the UCC. Standardization for triage included a consolidated red flag list that assists with receiving patients requiring triage timely, a documentation template to assist the triage nurse in guiding their assessment documentation and ensure consistency of data collection among triage nurses, and a guided triage assessment training that outlined a target time to perform and complete a focused assessment (nurses completed a 6 minute assessment determined by the organization standard protocol) (Private Organization Online Training Forum, 2018).

The adopt phase consisted of an in-person assessment training that included a review of the consolidated red flag list, the triage assessment algorithm, the documentation template and the online triage training module which included a visual demonstration of a triage assessment. This module was a requirement for all UCC RNs to complete. The new triage process was intended to; provide the triage nurses with education to enhance triage skills, provide an efficient method of gathering key assessment data during the triage process, and maximize triage efficiency to promote and support safe, timely, and quality patient assessments and care.

Procedure

Following IRB approval, a meeting was held with all UCC stakeholders (physician leadership and management including department supervisors) to discuss the department training and roll-out plan. This included the recommendation to present the information to the nurses during their staff meeting as well as via email and posted flyers. All stakeholders were copied on any email communication regarding the project to keep them updated on the project progress. The following PDSA steps were presented to all stakeholders as a review of the plan and project goals.

In the Plan stage, the problem of not having a triage standardized process was already identified. It is also the stage where the project aims were discussed with the stakeholders to obtain their buy-in and approval. The goals of this project outlining a standardized triage process to improve efficiency in the triage area was also presented during this stage. A second meeting with the project stakeholders was held to present the education and training plan for all UCC RNs and affiliated members including the department charge nurses who would be performing evaluation audits. The training required for this project included two components; an in-person skills training that will be performed by the project leader assigned to work with the department and an online assessment training module. The training for the UCC charge nurses included a requirement to complete the same training that the UCC RNs had and an additional requirement to complete a review of the evaluation tools (see Appendix B & D) that were used to evaluate the efficacy of triage assessment training, the accuracy of assigning acuities, and evaluating the reduction in total triage time (currently averaging anywhere from nine up to twenty-two minutes).

In the Do stage, the project leader obtained approval for the consolidated single red flag list from the stakeholders (UCC management team and physician leadership). This red flag list is essential in the front reception area as patients check in to be seen. It is the reference tool that is utilized by the UCC service representatives to be able to guide the patients to their next check in point (i.e. triage nurse). Once this single-sheet red flag list was approved, all other free-floating red flag symptom sheets were removed and discarded to avoid confusion. The Service Representatives were then in-serviced by the project leader to review the list and “flag” the patient charts by typing the words “Red Flag” on the patient check in notes followed by the check-in symptom (s). By flagging the charts on the electronic health record system, the Triage Nurse would be able to see and quickly identify and prioritize the patients requiring a triage assessment.

After the consolidation of the red flag list was completed, a meeting with the information technology (IT) team was held. The goal of this meeting was to create a “dot phrase” (i.e. a keyboard shortcut such as .uctriageassessment) that would populate a documentation template on the electronic health record (EHR) system for the triage nurses to be able to record their triage data. The template would ensure that every triage nurse would consistently record a standardized triage assessment note. Lacking a standardized triage assessment template to guide nurses in their documentation of data collection led to inconsistencies or missing critical assessment data.

The next step was to coordinate triage training. As previously presented, there were two components to the training: hands on training and an online video module. Each RN completed the online module as a pre-requisite to the in-person triage training. Hands on triage training was scheduled around the availability of the staff RNs. Due to

higher volumes of patients checking in during the implementation of the pilot, it was not possible to roll this triage training on a set date in a conference room setting. Instead, the project leader coordinated training dates with the department management team and performed training over several dates. Training was done in small groups of 1-3 nurses and an office space with a computer was reserved. Nurses who were unable to attend the training being offered by the department on the assigned dates had to schedule a make-up training session with one of the RN validators (Charge RNs).

Description of the Triage Training

The online video module was a pre-requisite step that all RNs had to complete online. The video is an existing online training tool that the organization utilizes in other departments and was now to be introduced to UCC nurses. It is approximately ten minutes in length and demonstrates a nurse performing a focused triage assessment, including vital signs, in approximately six minutes to help determine the acuity and prioritization. This training module provided a uniform method of performing triage to help standardize and reduce time wasted in triage (wasted time includes; time spent asking non-pertinent questions, time spent documenting information not pertaining to triage assessment, etc.). Nurses were required to print out their online video module completion certificate and submit it to the project leader. Once the project leader collected the completion certificates, the in-person skills training with the clinical educator were scheduled. However, due to the staffing constraints, there were modifications made to the required steps. Since there was availability to train the nurses in small groups, the online module was presented to the nurses before the hands-on training.

In the Study stage, chart audits and spot checks (through direct observation) were performed and results were documented by the project leader. Chart audits were performed to evaluate the documentation accuracy of the triage algorithm tool and to evaluate the consistency of triage documentation utilizing the standardized triage protocol. The purpose of the spot checks was to verify proper techniques in assessing vital signs and performing focused assessments based on the patient's chief complaints. For example, if a patient checks in with chest pain, the RN clinical supervisor will be assessing for the order of triage prioritization, getting a complete set of vital signs, the use of the triage protocol for chest pain, and that an immediate EKG was ordered. Both chart audits and direct observation results were analyzed.

In the Act stage, the project lead and stakeholders discussed the results. The pilot demonstrated success in the implementation of the triage process and the receptiveness of the staff. However, it was identified that a plan of action for sustainability needed to be developed to ensure ongoing adherence to the triage protocol. This will include additional training of the charge nurses to include a required daily huddle for a consecutive 2 weeks to remind staff about the expectation of the documentation of red flag patients and additional chart audits. This triage protocol education/training will need to be performed quarterly for the first year and then annually to ensure ongoing skills competency. A discussion of a plan for electronically tracking patient acuity was also discussed. This will require collaboration with the information technology (IT) department.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

To evaluate the training and adherence to the triage protocol and accuracy of triage documentation, a manual triage tracking process was developed. The following data were collected: 1) Patient Check In Time, 2) Gender, 3) Age, 4) Chief Complaint, 5) Chart Flagged 6) Vital Signs Complete Set, 6) Documentation Template Used, 7) Documentation Template Altered, and a Comments section (See Appendix D). This tracking form was used to collect and analyze the pilot project data.

Once the pre and post data was collected and analyzed the following was identified (see Table 2, Figure 2 & 3 below).

Table 2

Results: UC Patients and Staff Compliance Pre and Post Implementation

	Pre	Post
Total Patients presented to UC	440	582
Total Patients presenting to UC with red flags	131	200
Total patients with red flags where appropriate dot phrase used	56	196
Total patients where all components of vitals were completed	0	150
	Pre	Post
% Compliance with red flags	11%	42%
% compliance with dot phrase	43%	98%
% compliance with all VS completed	0%	75%

Figure 2 Results: Patient Volume Data

Figure 3: Results: Staff Compliance

Baseline data were collected by performing chart audits and looking at urgent care patient volume (pre and post). Data were obtained before and after implementation by extraction from the two of the busiest days of the week, Mondays and Fridays. The Urgent Care services an approximate average of 300 patients a day. Education and training were performed with 13 RNs and 3 Service Reps. Data were organized and analyzed by personal computer using Microsoft Office Pro Plus 365 Excel 2020 version. Data analysis showed that 32% of the total volume of patients who checked in to Urgent Care reported critical symptoms categorized as “red flags”. Patients who registered with the urgent care service representatives and reported a red flag symptom were supposed to be routed to the triage nurse for an assessment. During the pre-implementation data collection, patients who required a triage assessment were not flagged appropriately, resulting in 89% of the qualifying patients not being triaged. There was a compliance rate of 11% for patient charts that were appropriately identified and documented as “red flag”. Additionally, triage nurses had a compliance rate of 43% for appropriate triage documentation. There was a 0% compliance rate for documenting all vital signs.

Post implementation data indicated improvement in all areas. The service representatives showed appropriate flagging of charts at a 42% compliance rate compared to only 11% at baseline. The triage nurses also demonstrated improvement with appropriate utilization of the dot phrase and collection and documentation of a complete set of vital signs. Compliance rate for appropriate use of the dot phrase documentation template went from 43% to 98% compliance rate post implementation. A complete set of vital signs documentation compliance rate increased from 0% to 75%.

DISCUSSION

The goal of this project was to strengthen triage nursing assessment skills and provide triage nurses with an efficient standardized method for gathering key assessment data during the triage process. Adherence to the new triage protocol was evaluated using spot checks and chart audits for compliance and sustainability. These combined efforts ensure that triage acuity is correctly applied thus increasing patient safety. In the pilot project setting, it was an organizational and department goal to introduce a standardized triage process in the UCC setting, minimizing delay of care and poor patient outcomes. As a result, it was identified that UCCs lack uniformity and standardization in their triage process (Carroll et al, 2019). These findings were consistent with prior studies that looked at the efficacy of triage education and the effect on nursing's ability to adequately assess and minimize delay of care for patients (Goransson, Persson, & Abelson, 2020; Faheim et al., 2019; Carrol et al., 2019).

In order to sustain adherence to the triage assessment protocol, it will be necessary for ongoing in-services and huddles to ensure that both the service representatives and triage nurses see this as a daily requirement vs. a one-time project implementation. Ongoing monitoring and skill competency have been identified as an effective way to keep nurses engaged and accountable in an area that is critical to patient care (Gorasson, Persson, & Abelson, 2020; Faheim et al., 2019). During this project, service representatives were more inclined to “flag” patient charts accordingly while they were being observed. Triage Nurses were also compliant with vital sign collection and triage assessment documentation when being directly observed. However, when post-implementation data were extracted from chart audits, it revealed that there were still

significant inconsistencies with the accuracy of assessment data collection. There were about 46% of patient charts that were not flagged accordingly indicating that the service representatives deviated away from their expected check-in task when they were not being closely supervised. A recent study showed that when ongoing education and training is not in place, it leads to disengagement and non-adherence within a three-month period (Goransson, Persson, & Abellsson, 2020).

Triage nurses, however, were able to capture a majority of patients who required triage despite the charts not being adequately flagged by the service representatives. This required the triage nurses to scan through every patient chart and read all chief complaints to identify red flags and call the patients to the triage station for an assessment. The triage nurses were then able to use the documentation template for all of the patients that they triaged.

Feedback obtained from the project participants was positive and supportive of the standardized triage protocol. Nurses verbally expressed to their manager that they felt more confident in their skills and ability to appropriately prioritize care for patients after reviewing the triage protocol. Staff members also acknowledged that ongoing training would be beneficial as staff turnover is common in the department and on-call staff, who do not work daily, may benefit from a “refresher” throughout the year.

Limitations

There were several limitations that were identified with the implementation of this project. There was a short post evaluation period due to delays in obtaining approval for all components of the project. All UCC staff members were not trained because some staff were on a leave of absence. In addition, other limitations included difficulty in

ongoing supervision of staff and performing spot checks, additional education and training sessions for those staff members who were on leave of absence, and the overall timing of the evaluation period which was too short to obtain more post-data.

Implications for Practice

Urgent care centers would benefit from the use of a standardized triage protocol as demonstrated by this project. Patients entering the urgent care clinic may present with symptoms that need immediate medical intervention. Patient safety is a priority. In order to ensure appropriate assessment of the efficacy of the protocol across all UCC, wider dissemination and evaluation of the triage training protocol is needed.

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APPENDIX A

PERMISSION TO USE PDSA MODEL

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APPENDIX B

URGENT CARE TRIAGE ALGORITHM

UC Triage Algorithm

<p>A EMERGENCY-- High acuity with immediate MD notification.</p> <p>Is the patient in respiratory distress? Is the patient experiencing shortness of breath with chest pain? Is the patient unable to speak in full sentences?</p> <p>Is the patient complaining of chest pain? Is the pain a severe, tearing pain radiating to back? Has the patient had a prior heart attack or stent and is this pain similar to that event? Did the chest pain begin while at rest or worsen with exertion? Is patient's coloring blue or grey to the face, lips, earlobes, or fingernails?</p> <p>Is the patient presenting with new on-set of stroke-like symptoms? Does the patient have facial drooping, unilateral weakness or slurred speech? Is the patient complaining of the "worst headache of my life"?</p> <p>Is the patient hypoglycemic: experiencing loss of consciousness and diaphoretic? Does the patient have severe abdominal pain? Is the patient experiencing vaginal bleeding with possible pregnancy at less than 20 weeks with unstable vital signs? Is the patient an infant < 30 days with a pulse of 60 or less? Is the patient less than or equal to 3 months of age presenting with SOB? Pediatric patients presenting with Head injuries, lacerations, suspicion of broken bones, or burns</p>	<p>YES → Bring patient directly back and alert the MD to the room immediately; anticipate treatment necessary to stabilize the patient</p> <p>↓ NO</p>
<p>B URGENT-- High acuity without immediate MD notification.</p> <p>Is the patient complaining of non-pleuritic chest pain that is unrelieved with rest? Is the patient experiencing heart palpitations that are new or associated with the chest pain? Does the patient have moderate abdominal pain? Did the patient sustain a loss of consciousness or altered mental status? Is the patient complaining of a severe headache with fever and unable to bend chin to chest? Is the patient's BP < 100/60 and not baseline for them? Is the patient's BP > 180/120? Is the patient's pulse oximeter reading < 90% at room air? Is there vaginal bleeding in pregnancy less than 20 weeks with stable vital signs? Is the patient receiving chemotherapy and has a fever? Is the patient experiencing moderate to severe anxiety or distress? Is the patient displaying signs of severe pain such as facial grimacing, body posturing, changes in V/S such as tachycardia, or increased RR? Is this a child < 2 years of age presenting with a productive cough or a bark-like cough? Is this an infant or a child < 2 years old with RR of 60 or greater, and or capillary refill of greater than 3 seconds or temperature >100.4F orally or 101.4 rectally?</p>	<p>YES → Make sure patient is next to be seen</p> <p>↓ NO</p>
<p>C NON-URGENT</p> <p>Does the patient have diarrhea or vomiting? Does the patient need a work-up? Does the patient have a rash?</p>	
<p>D FAST TRACK</p> <p>Does the patient have symptoms of a urinary tract infection, upper respiratory infection, or extremity injury without a laceration? Is the patient here for a medication refill, or DMI?</p>	

APPENDIX C

RED FLAG LIST (S)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Abdominal Pain (including pregnancy) ❖ Bleeding (GI) ❖ Bloody Diarrhea ❖ Bradycardia ❖ Burn ❖ Chest Pain ❖ CHF ❖ Confusion or Mental Status Change ❖ Constant Cough (that limits ability to breathe well) ❖ COPD ❖ Dark Green Vomiting ❖ Drug Overdose / Withdrawal / Poisoning ❖ Dyspnea ❖ Fever with Stiff Neck ❖ Foreign Body, Ingested ❖ Hallucination ❖ Headache ❖ Head Injury ❖ Heat Exhaustion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Hypertension, Symptomatic ❖ Hypotension ❖ Irregular Heartbeat ❖ Lethargy ❖ Motor Vehicle Accident (MVA) with Neck Pain ❖ Needle Stick ❖ Numbness of Extremity or Facial Droop ❖ Palpitations ❖ Peritonsillar Abscess ❖ Rectal Bleeding (Painful or Painless) ❖ Seizure, Febrile or Afebrile ❖ Severe Female Pelvic Pain ❖ Sore Throat (with or without drooling) or has complaints of trismus (a spasm of the jaw muscles that makes it difficult to open the mouth) ❖ Syncope ❖ Testicular Pain (Mild-Moderate, Severe) ❖ Trauma to Chest / Abdomen / Head with deformity of extremity ❖ Vaginal Bleeding (Pregnancy-Related)
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- ❖ Rash + Fever
- ❖ Rash + Sore Throat
- ❖ Verbalized Exposure to Measles

- ❖ Allergic Reactions
- ❖ Slurred Speech
- ❖ Suicidal Ideation

- ❖ Can't Wake My Baby
- ❖ Chest Pain
- ❖ Continuous Crying
- ❖ Danger to Self or Others
- ❖ High or Prolonged Fever
- ❖ Ingestion
- ❖ Injury
- ❖ Lethargic

- ❖ Rash
- ❖ Respiratory
- ❖ Seizure
- ❖ Severe Abdominal Pain
- ❖ Severe Headache
- ❖ Severe Vomiting
- ❖ Stiff Neck and Fever
- ❖ Unable to Void

APPENDIX D

TRIAGE TRACKING SPREADSHEET

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D15

DATA DICTIONARY

- Gender: Male (M) = 1, Female (F) = 2
- Age:
 1. infant to 14
 2. 15 to 44
 3. 45 to older
- Check-In Time:
 1. (9:00AM-12:00PM) AM Shift
 2. (1:00PM-3:00PM) PM Shift
 3. (6:00PM-9:00PM) N/E Shift
- Chief Complaint (CC):
 1. Shortness of Breath
 2. Curbac (palpitations, chest pain, chest pressure)
 3. Stroke Symptoms (slurred speech, hemiparesis)
 4. Lacerations (bleeding)
 5. Other Red Flag Symptoms
- Chart Flagged:
 1. Yes
 2. No
- Vital Signs Complete:
 1. Yes
 2. No
- Documentation Template Used:
 1. Yes
 2. No
- Documentation Template Altered (changed by the nurse):
 1. Yes
 2. No
- Patient Disposition After Triage:
 1. Waiting Room/Lobby
 2. Exam Room
 3. X-Ray

DATA DICTIONARY (S1)10-7-19 (Baseline MON) (S2)10-11-19 (Baseline FRI) (S3)01-20-20 (Pr...

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O3

DNP: Process Improvement for Screening Patients in the Urgent Care (Triage Data)

DATE: 10/7/2019 (MON) TOTAL CENSUS: 205

Check In Time	Gender	Age	Chief Complaint	Chart Flagged (yes=1, No=2)	Vital signs Complete Set (yes=1, No=2)	doc template (yes=1, No=2)	doc template altered (yes=1, No=2)	Comments	Vital Signs Complete Set (Yes=1, No=2)	Total
1	1	2	2, 3, 5	1	2	2	1	EKG @ 10:27AM	1	0
2	1	2	1	5	1	2	1		2	82
3	1	1	2	2	1	2	1			
4	1	1	2, 4, 5	1	2	1	1			82
5	1	2	2	2	1	2	1	Chemo pt sent to lobby		
6	1	1	2, 1, 5	1	2	1	1			
7	1	1	3, 1, 2, 5	1	2	1	1			
8	2	2	2, 2, 5	1	2	1	1			15
9	2	1	2	5	1	2	1	Noted as "triage please" vs "RED FLAG"	1	67
10	2	1	2	4	1	2	1	noted as "VS please" vs "RED FLAG"		
11	2	2	2, 2, 5	1	2	1	1	Pt sent to lobby, EKG @ 2:55pm		
12	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	EKG @ 4:32pm		

DATA DICTIONARY (S1)10-7-19 (Baseline MON) (S2)10-11-19 (Baseline FRI) (S3)01-20-20 (Pr...